

Modeling Decarbonization Pathways for the Power Sector of Developing Countries: The case of Nepal

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1.1 Background and Rationale

- Nepal has pledged to reduce GHG emissions by 26.8% by 2035 and achieve net-zero CO₂ by 2045.
- The power system is heavily reliant on hydropower (>90%), yet seasonal variability and climate risks (droughts, floods, glacial lake outburst floods) threaten system reliability.
- Nepal's high-heat industries face severe energy insecurity, as total coal demand far exceeds supply, with the cement sector alone needing 35,000 TPD but receiving only about 20%.
- Demand is expected to triple by 2050 due to electrification of cooking, transport, and industry.

1.2 Research Question

- To what extent do rapid electric-vehicle adoption, widespread electric cooking, and industrial fuel switching (including RDF utilization) influence energy security, reduce fossil-fuel dependence and energy imports, and relate to changes in economy-wide GHG emissions?

Source: NEA

Baseline (BAU)

No Carbon Target

- Historical hydro-dominance continues
- Limited penetration of solar/wind and storage
- Increasing imports in dry seasons

Accelerated Electrification & RDF Utilization (REW-Diversification)

High electrification by 2045 but not full net-zero.

- Transport electrification to near-total by 2045
- Electric cooking to 50% by 2050, LPG phased out by 2045
- Industrial RDF co-firing and electrification to 50% by 2045.

Net Zero Emission (NZE)

REW- Diversification + a binding net-zero cap in 2050

- Net-zero CO₂ by 2050
- Targeted CCS for residuals
- Renewables dominate all sectors

3. Energy Mix

4. Sectoral Overview

Industrial High Heat Sector- Consumption

Residential Cooking Consumption

Transport Sector (Bus/Car/ Motorcycle)- Consumption

Discounted Total Cost

	Discounted Total Cost (in billion)	Annualized Investment Cost	Percentage of GDP
BAU	US\$ 84.502	US\$ 0.794	2%
REW-Diversification	US\$ 83.055	US\$ 1.520	4%
NZE	US\$ 83.841	US\$ 1.606	4%
GDP: US\$ 42.91 billion in 2024			

6. Annual Emission

Total Annual Emission

Cost of Emission Reduction (USD/Ton)	
REW-Diversification	230
NZE	224

Accelerated electrification of transport, cooking, and industry, combined offers Nepal the fastest route to strengthen energy security, cut fuel imports, and reduce economy-wide emissions while maintaining affordability.

7.1 Decisions for the Next Year

- Enact a Net-Zero law with binding 2050 cap to guide investments across all scenarios.
- Launch a national electric-cooking program with appliance financing and LPG phase-down.
- Issue EV adoption standards and incentives (cars 90% and buses 70% by 2030).
- Approve industrial RDF and modern biomass co-firing guidelines and initiate pilots in cement and brick industries.

7.2 Priority Actions to 2030

- Complete a nationwide EV-charging corridor and enforce fleet electrification milestones.
- Expand electric cooking to 40% of households and end new LPG connections.
- Scale RDF co-firing to 25–30% of industrial high-heat demand.

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